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New Epitaphs from Cibyra and Gölhisar-II

Elif ALTEN GÜLER

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New Epitaphs from Cibyra and Gölhisar-II

Kibyra ve Gölhisar'dan Yeni Mezar Yazıtları-II

Elif ALTEN GÜLER *

Abstract: This study introduces eight epitaphs found during the field survey and excavations carried out in both Cibyra and its territory within 2012-2013 and brought to the excavation house. The first belongs to Ammia set up by her friend Helike. The second is for Eirene, wife of Epithymetos. The third is for Polla, wife for Troilos. The fourth is a funerary altar for Ammia, daughter of Pankrates, with garlands and bukranon. The fifth is for the parent of Lucius and Titus. And other two are for wife of Trophimos and for the parents of Cl. Logos. The last one is of round altar shape with garlands, also it is unknown by/for whom it was set this up. All the inscriptions are dated between the 1st century BC and IIIrd century AD taking into account the characterization of the letters of the inscriptions and the ornamental studies.

Keywords: Cibyra, Gölhisar, Epitaph, Epigraphy

Öz: Bu çalışmada, Kibyra ve territoryumunda yapılan yüzey ve kazı çalışmaları sonucunda 2012 ve 2013 yılında ele geçip kazı evine getirilen mezar yazıtları tanıtılacaktır. İlki, arkadaşı Helike'nin Ammia için yaptırdığı mezar stelidir. İkincisi, Epithymetos'un eşi Eirene içindir. Üçüncüsü, Troilos'un eşi Polla için yapılandır. Dördüncü yazıt, Pankrates kızı Ammia için yapılan girlandlı ve boğa başlı mezar sunağıdır. Beşinci yazıtta Lucius ve Titus'un anne ve babaları için yaptırdığı yazıttır. İkisi ise, Trophimos'un karısı için yaptırdığı ve Cl. Logos'un anne ve babası için olan yazıtlardır. Sonuncu yazıt ise kim için ve kim tarafından yapıldığı bilinmeyen girlandlı silindir formlu altardır. Buradaki tüm yazıtlar harf karakterleri ile bezemeleri dikkate alınarak genel olarak MÖ I. yüzyıl – MS III. yüzyıl arasına tarihlendirilebilirler.

Anahtar sözcükler: Kibyra, Gölhisar, Mezar Yazıtı, Epigrafi

1. Epitaph of Ammia

A cylindrical funerary altar made of marble found at Cibyra's Eastern Necropolis in 2012¹. The upper and the lower parts are profiled. The stele carries a four-lined inscription on its body. It is well-preserved, however there are some fractures on the upper part. The top of the stone is roughing. The letter H's (= *eta*) bar carved free from the lines, in the middle of the letter without touching the both lines. The *rho* (P) is curved inward, *phi* (φ) is written long but small semicircular in the center. These features indicate that the inscription should be dated Roman Imperial Period.

Findspot: Between the modern road and northern necropolis road.

Dimensions: h.: 0.94 m; d.: 0.40 m; l.h.: 0.042-0.045 m.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. AD (according to lettering).

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¹ For the inscriptions found in the Eastern Necropolis see Kileci – Şimşek 2019; Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019.

- Ἑλίκη Τυρά-
 2 ννου ὡς Ἀμμία
 τῆ φιλή μνίας
 4 χάριν.

Helike, daughter of Tyrannos (set this up) for her friend Ammia, in memory.

The name of Helike is here recorded in the city for the first time. However, it is known in Asia Minor, both in Nicomedia and Dorylaion². On the other hand, the name Tyrannos is known from an epitaph set up for Claudius Tyrannos and his wife Philete, dated to I-IInd AD and in the same century there is also one Tyrannos who is the father of Orestes³ in Cibyra.

The name Ammia is known from the city for four times⁴, however this study adds two more persons to this name, other than this stele see here no. 5. The term μνίας χάριν is recorded before in the epitaphs found in Cibyra⁵, used as μνείας χάριν or μνήμης χάριν.

2. Epitaph of Eirene

A cylindrical funerary altar made of limestone. On top is a high profile. The upper part is with profil, but the lower part is broken. On the top, there is a hole. The body part is divided into three parts (0.18x0.23x0.17 m). The first two part bears five-line inscription. The inscription is well-preserved. The findspot is unknown, it was brought to the excavation house from Gölhisar.

Findspot: Gölhisar.

Dimensions: h.: 0.82 m; d.: 0.34 m; l.h.: 0.03-0.04 m.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. AD (according to *omega*).

- Ἐπιθύμητος
 2 Εἰρήνη τῆ γλυκυ-
 τάτη γυναῖκι
 4 μνείας ἔνεκα
 καὶ ἑαυτῷ ζῶν

Epithymetos, (set this up) for Eirene, the sweetest wife, in memory and for himself while he is living.

The name Epithymetos is here recorded in the city for the

² For Nicomedeia see *LGPN Va* and for Dorylaion see *LGPN Vc*.

³ For Cl. Tyrannus: *IKibyra 151*: Κλ(αύδιος) · Τύραννος ἑαυτῷ καὶ Φιλῆτῃ τῆ γυναικὶ ζῶντες σὺν τῷ ὑποκειμένῳ ἔμπροσθε[ν] | τοῦ βωμικοῦ οἴκῳ | κενώματος ΠΗΕ [- - -][[- - (?) - -]]; Tyrannus as father: **301**: Ὁρέστης Τυράννου | τὸ μνημεῖον σὺν τῷ οἴκῳ καὶ τῆ ἐν αὐτῷ σορῶ | κατεσκευάσθη ☉ Τάτει | τῆ γυναικὶ καὶ ἑαυτῷ ζῶντι, ἐν ᾗ τεθή[σονται] αὐτοὶ μόνου· ἐὰν δέ | τις ἐνχειρήσῃ θεῖναι ἔτερον ἐν τῇ σορῶ, ἀποδώσει τῷ φίσκῳ δηνάρι[α -].

⁴ *IKibyra 109*; 133-134, 365.

⁵ *IKibyra 111*; 115; 164; 171; 213; 258.

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first time and it is rarely found in Anatolia. It has been attested in Paphlagonia (Marek 1993, 194, 24), Phrygia (*SEG* VI 266) and Lykia (*TAM* II 615). The name Eirene is, however, known from Cibyra, see *IKibyra* 220, 221, 293. *μνείας ἔνεκα* is a term frequently employed on epitaphs⁶, for the similar writing of this term see above no. 1.

3. Epitaph of Polla

A well-preserved cylindrical funerary altar made of marble, with a high profile on top. The findspot is unknown, brought to the excavation house from Gölhisar. The inscription is whole and preserved. There is a lacuna on the third line due to a break. Alpha is written with broken bar, *epsilon*'s (E) middle bar in free from the letter, and *omega* (Ω) written in two styles, one is curved inward without a bar under it, the other has two bars.

Findspot: Gölhisar.

Dimensions: h.: 1.025 m; d.: 0.50 m; l.h.: 0.02-0.03 m.

Date: I-IInd cent. AD (according to lettering).

- Τροῖλος Ἀνρέ-
 2 ου Πώλλα τῆ γυναι-
 κι καὶ αὐ^{vac.} τῶ ζῶν-
 4 τι.

Troilos son of Andreas (set this up) for his wife Polla and himself while he is living.

The name Troilos is a very pervasive in the city⁷. The name Andreas is derived from the Hellenic word ὁ ἀνὴρ meaning 'a man' to ἡ ἀνδρεία (bravery)⁸, which attested mostly on epitaphs in Cibyra⁹. This is the first attestation from Cibyra of the name Polla (Πώλλα). This name has been attested twice in Pisidia¹⁰.

4. Funerary Altar of Ammia

An *ostotheke* made of marble, with garlands and bucranium, brought to the excavation house from the Cibyra's Eastern Necropolis in 2013. There are bands tied on top of the heads that belong to garlands. The *taeniae* are flat and tasseled, fall between the fruits carved on the garlands. The *ostotheke* carries two inscriptions, one of which is survived, has three-line inscription. The other inscription carved on the left side of the existing one, but it was removed. There remain only few surviving letters. On the inscription, the alpha is written with broken bar.

Findspot: Eastern Necropolis, upper part of the monumental tombs.

Dimensions: h.: body: 1.05 m - lid: 0.21 m; d.: 0.70 m; l.h.: 0.025 m.

Date: Ist century B.C. (according to the ornaments).

⁶ E.g. *IKibyra* 106, 109, 110, 126, 142, 144, 168, 173, 188, 214-216, 222, 227.

⁷ For Troilos see *IKibyra* 39; 41; 42A-E; 44A-E; 47; 53; 87; 97; 112; 113; 115; 119; 183; 192; 203; 205; 209; 238; 249; 254; 255; 274; 298; 346; 347; 348; 349; 350; 351; 359; 370; Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019, 286.

⁸ Bailly 1935, 148 s.v. ἀνδρεία, ἡ.

⁹ *IKibyra* 111; 171; 243; 286; 399.

¹⁰ Olbasa: *SEG* XLVIII, 1546. Antiokheia (Yalvaç): Levick 1967, 116.

Ἀμμίαν Πανκράτους
2 γυναίκα Μοαγέτου
καὶ Γῆ Νειάρχου.

In honor of Ammia, the daughter of Pankrates and wife of Moagetes and Ge, the daughter of Nearkhos (set this up).

The name Pankrates¹¹ is known from the city. The name Moagetes is known from the city as a tyrant told by Strabo (XIII. 4. 17), and from the Roman-Cibyra treaty as one of the dynasts¹². While Ammia is recorded four times¹³, Nearkhos was a well-known name in Cibyra¹⁴. There is also an honorary inscription, previously recorded, that bears the same names “Ge, the daughter of Nearkhos”¹⁵.

On the left side of the inscription above, there is also two-line inscription, which was removed. It is unknown whether the inscription above has a connection with this removed inscription. Though there is a space between them. Since the inscription was removed, it is not legible, and therefore is impossible to track the lines. This removal may refer a second usage or somehow it was purchased by another person. The inscription removed is as follows:

M[-----]
2 κ[αί?-----]
[— μνήμης ἔνεκ]ε.

*M... [(set this up) for n.n. and? n.n.],
in memory.*

According to the studies carried out in Cibyra, cremation is mostly seen in the Hellenistic Period, gives it place to inhumation during the first century AD. The cremation starts to be seen during the Antonine Period in the eastern necropolis¹⁶. This *ostotheke* is dated to the Hellenistic Period, especially to the 1st century BC, according to the form of the ornaments. However, the lettering of the first inscription, which is legible, dates itself to the Roman Imperial Period, especially to the IInd-IIIrd century AD. If so, the name Moagetes is attested for the first time in the Roman Period.

5. Epitaph of Eugeneia and Titus

A well-preserved cylindrical funerary altar made of limestone, can be seen today in Gölhisar Meydan Çeşme Parkı. It is well-preserved, profiled on both lower and upper parts, processed in cyma form. All the letters of the stone with seven lines of the inscription are protected and complete.

¹¹ *IKibyra* 42A; 44A; 51; 214; 300; 312; 363; Kileci 2019, 343; Kileci – Şimşek 2019, 272.

¹² Özüdoğru 2018a, 754. For the recorded evidences of the name Moagates in the region see also *SEG XVIII* 570, *LGN Vc* s.v. Μοαγέτης.

¹³ *IKibyra* 109, 133, 134, 365. For others see above no. 1.

¹⁴ *IKibyra* 49; 162; 217; 262; 279; 288; Alten-Güler 2019, 337.

¹⁵ *IKibyra* 49. For other names see *IKibyra* 113, 198, 230, 325.

¹⁶ For the cremation and the burial system in Cibyra see Özüdoğru 2018b, 111-113; Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019, 276.

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The letter sigma is as C and A (alpha) is with broken bar. There are two types of H (eta). In line 4, H is written with a separate bar, and in line 6 it is seen as H.

Findspot: Unknown.

Dimensions: h.: 1.07 m; d.: 0.65 m; l.h.: 0.03-04 m.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. AD (according to lettering).

- Λούκιος
 2 καὶ Τίτος
 Εὐγενέα
 4 μητρὶ καὶ
 Τίτῳ πατρὶ
 6 μνήμης ἔν-
 εκα.

Lucius and Titus (set this up) for their mother Eugene(i)a and father Titus, in memory.

Both the names Lucius and Titus have been recorded before at Cibyra¹⁷. Eugenea/Eugeneia derives from εὐγενής, ἑς meaning "high descent"¹⁸. This name is not attested before in Cibyra, although it is known from Anatolia, from Cyme (*IKyme* 37), Hierapolis (Hicks 1890, 248, 19), Laodicia ad Lycum (*SEG LVI* 1510) and Pisidian Antiochia (*IK Antioche de Piside* 1).

6. Epitaph of Trophimos and his wife

A cylindrical funerary altar made of marble. The find spot is unknown whereas it was brought to the excavation house from Muftiate of Gölhisar. Stele is divided into three parts by carving the body (0.26x0.20x0.26 m). The lower and the upper parts are profiled and there are fractures on those parts. The body bears four-line inscription. The Alpha is written with broken bar.

Findspot: Gölhisar.

Dimensions: h.: 0.93 m; d.: 0.50 m; l.h.: 0.03 m.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. AD (according to lettering).

- Τρώφιμος Ἰνδοῦ
 2 ἑαυτῷ ζῶν καὶ τῷ
 πατρὶ, γυναικὶ μνή-
 4 μης ἔνεκε[ν].

Trophimos, son of Indos, (set this up) living, for himself his father and his wife, in memory.

The name Trophimos is attested from the city before as Publius Claudius Trophimos (*IKibyra* 150) and Aurelius Trophimos (*IKibyra* 353). As to Indus, it is the name

¹⁷ For Lucius see *IKibyra* 82; 156; 193; 195; 242-3; 259; For Titus see *IKibyra* 55, 176, 248, 307, 345.

¹⁸ Liddle-Scott 1883, 596 s.v. εὐγενής, ἑς.; Bailly 1935, 827-828 s.v. εὐγενής, ἑς.

of the Dalaman river¹⁹. However this river's name was also used as a person name in antiquity. This name has been previously recorded in the regions of Cilicia-Isauria, Lycaonia, Pamphylia and Pisidia²⁰. In the city, it is known from an epitaph that reads Indonis and Indonius, as person names derivings from the river's name²¹.

7. Epitaph of Claudi(u)s Logos and Eirene

A cylindrical funerary altar made of marble, found at the street leads to the stadium. The top is cut flat. The upper and the lower parts are with profile resembling a cyma. The body part is also divided into three parts (0.12x0.37x0.13 m). The body bears six-line inscription. The letter *sigma* is written in square shape.

Findspot: The street leads to the stadium, named as also Cibyra's Northern Necropolis Road.

Dimensions: h.: 0.86 m; d.: 0.56 m; l.h.: 0.04 m.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. AD (according to lettering).

Κλαύδης Λόγος

Κλαυδίω Λόγω

3 τῷ πατρὶ μνή-

μης ἔνεκεν

κὲ Εἰρήνη τῇ

6 μητρὶ ζώση.

Claudi(u)s Logos (set this up) for his father, Claudius Logus, in memory, and for his mother Eirene while she is living.

For the omitting of /o/ in the *nomen gentilicium* Κλαύδης (= Claudis) see Gignac 1976, 227-228; Brixhe 1976, 49-50; and see Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019, 287. However, it can also be seen at the line 2 with his father's name, written as Κλαυδίω. The name Logos has not been previously attested in Cibyra before. The name Eirene is well attested in Cibyra²², see also above no. 3.

8. Altar Shaped Epitaph with Garland

An altar shaped epitaph made of limestone found in Gölhisar, however its findspot is unknown. The upper and the lower parts are profiled. The top of the stele is flat. The upper and lower parts are profiled. The body is carved with low relief bucranium, laureated garlands, and there are bands on the heads of the bulls. The *taeniae* of the bands are flat and tasseled, fall between the garlands. The heads of the bulls are in shape of a skull with skin. Their faces are treated undetailed, boned and rough²³. The upper part bears two-lined inscription written irregularly. Alpha is written with broken bar, and *epsilon's* (E) middle bar in free from the letter. According to lettering is it dated to Roman Imperial Period.

¹⁹ For the river see Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019, 281 fn. 12.

²⁰ Cilicia-Isauria: Heberday – Wilhelm 1896, 151; Bean – Mitford 1970, 168, for more see *LGPN Vb*; Lycaonia: *MAMA VIII*, 131; Pamphylia: Heberday – Wilhelm 1896, 140; Pisidia: Keil *et al.* 1953, 53.

²¹ Alten-Güler – Şimşek 2019, 279.

²² *IKibyra* 220, 221, 293.

²³ For the master thesis about the *Kibyra altars embossed type and the workshop* see Tarkan 2011; also pages 29; 34-35; and also see Berges 1986. D. Tarkan (2011, 18) asserts that it is written χαῖρε as a fragment on the body of the stele, however it is obvious that it is written as χρηστὲ χαῖρε.

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Findspot: Gölhisar.

Dimensions: h.: 0.645 m; d.: 0.45 m; l.h.: 0.03-0.55 m.

Date: First half of the 1st century AD (according to ornaments).

χρηστὲ χαῖρε. *Greetings! /or/ Farewell!*

The term *χρηστὲ χαῖρε* is known from the epitaphs found in Kibyra, see *IKibyra* 152, 201. This term is used for the expression as a symbol of death, which is explained as a praised person during his/her lifetime. It is written mostly in *vocativus singularis*. To Th. Corsten, it is used for slaves, see *IKibyra* 152. It is recorded before in Asia Minor in Isinda, dated to I-IInd AD, and in Apameia Kelainai²⁴. Based upon the epigraphical sources, *χρηστὲ χαῖρε*²⁵ is used frequently on the epitaphs found in Attika, Megaris, Oropia and Boiotia see in general *IG* II, IV, VII. Some of them are translated as “salve” and some of them as “farewell”. In a bilingual inscription found in Rheneia, Greece, the latin “salve” is written as “*χρηστὲ χαῖρε*” in ancient Greek²⁶.

D. Noy (2017, 123) highlightens that the stelae set up in local styles, on which this term is carved are used by the Delian migrants.

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²⁴ For Isinda see French 1994, 7; for Apameia Kelainai see *IGR* IV 796. For the examples in Karia see McCabe 1991, 137, 140, 151, 153, 154, 163, 170; and in Ionia see McCabe 1986, 155, 160, 194, 197, 208, 209, 215.

²⁵ This term is also used on the epitaphs belong to families, when especially there is a decision. For more detail see Buresch 1894; Ehrhardt 1994; Strubbe 1998, 70 dp. 78; Kuhn 2017, 211.

²⁶ See *CIL* III.7242; VI.12904.

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